

Evaluating charge carrier transition in copper–zinc and copper-copper heterostructure photocathodes towards conversion of solar energy into fuels

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Abstract: Production of fuels from CO₂ is an important research area not only due to its potential contribution to counteracting climate change but also for saving fossil carbon resources through the recycling of carbon. Various methods of CO₂ utilization are under intensive study, including photocatalysis, a promising, environmentally friendly technique of solar to chemical energy conversion.

Among many other heterogeneous photocatalysts, copper-based materials are considered as particularly interesting due to their high photoactivity under visible light, low toxicity, and huge abundance of copper. We have studied copper-copper and copper-zinc heterostructures that showed activity towards the production of hydrogen as well as the reduction of carbon dioxide in photocatalytic and photoelectrochemical systems. Our goal was to investigate the fate of photogenerated charge carriers. Processes such as charge separation, recombination, transfer, and trapping are responsible for crucial properties of photomaterials: their long-term activity, efficiency, and stability.

A fully understanding of photo(electro)catalysis requires holistic insight at the interface. To solve the problem, we must look at the system from different perspectives, using different "eyes" in sync to look for interrelated events. By combining classic electrochemical techniques, photoelectrochemical measurements, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, and other spectroscopic tools, including synchrotron-based techniques, we created a holistic investigation methodology that helped us understand the behavior of our materials in the context of their stability and activity. By using their holistic investigation we studied copper/copper and copper/zinc heterostructures in both, photocatalytic and photoelectrochemical systems. As a target reaction, we investigated the reduction of water to hydrogen and the reduction of carbon dioxide to C1 and C2 molecules.

Biography of presenting author: Dr. Tomasz Baran is a postdoctoral researcher at Interuniversity Consortium on Chemical Reactivity and Catalysis (CIRCC) and Innovative Catalysis for Carbon Recycling (IC2R) in Italy. He is also a R&D director and co-founder of the research center SajTom Light Future in Poland. His work is focused on photocatalytic and photoelectrochemical processes, in particular solar fuel production. He is author of more than 30 scientific papers in international journals. Participant in a few former ICCDU meetings.

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